

Attitude of Business Educators in Adopting Artificial Intelligence Application in Teaching Business Education Courses in Rivers State Universities

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ABSTRACT

This research work focused on attitude of Business Educators toward adopting artificial intelligence applications in teaching Business Education courses in Universities in Rivers State. two research questions and hypotheses were formulated and tested for the study. The study adopted the descriptive survey research design, the area of the study is Universities in Rivers State Precisely Public Universities offering Business Education programme. The instrument for data collection was a self-structured questionnaire tagged “Attitude of Business Educators Toward Adopting Artificial Intelligence Applications. Two experts from Department of Business Education and one expert in measurement and evaluation all of Rivers State University validated the instrument. All the inputs and corrections from the experts were used to modify the research instrument before administration. Reliability level for the instruments was established using a test-re-test method. Pearson’s Product Moment Correlation Coefficient was used to analyse the set of data and the reliability levels were established at a coefficient (r) of 0.89 meaning the instrument is reliable for the study. Mean and standard deviation was used in answering the research questions while ANOVA was used in testing the hypotheses at 0.05% level of significance. The population of the study consisted of 47 Business Educators. Due to the fact that the population of the study is relatively small, census sampling method. This means that the entire respondents of forty-seven (47) Business Educators were used for analyses of the study. Analysis of data were done using mean and standard deviation to answer the 2 research questions, while the 2 hypotheses were tested using Anova at 0.05 level of significance. From the findings it was revealed that the finding of the study in research question one revealed that concern about potential job displacement, ethical concerns and implication, limitations faced by Business Educators, level of resistance faced by Business Educators, acceptability level of Business Educators in adopting artificial intelligence applications in teaching Business Education courses in Universities in Rivers State to a high extent. Based on the findings, the researcher recommended among others that educational policymakers and university management should build on the already high acceptability level by organizing regular hands-on workshops and certification programs on AI tools for teaching, to reinforce and expand Business Educators’ willingness to adopt these technologies across universities.

Keywords; Attitude, Business Educators, Artificial, Intelligence, Application

INTRODUCTION

The positive attitude is characterized by confidence, optimism, sincerity, and reliability. Onwuagboke in Wogboroma (2022) asserted that individuals with a positive attitude focus on the good rather than the bad in people, situations, and events. They view mistakes or failures as opportunities to learn and excel.

Meanwhile, the negative attitude is marked by hatred, pessimism, resentment, and doubt. That is, individuals with a negative attitude tend to ignore the good in situations and focus on the bad. They are likely to complain about changes and innovations rather than adapting to them, and they often blame others for their failures. It manifests in various forms, from scepticism to outright hostility, and can significantly impact an individual's personal and professional life. Negative attitude can be caused by an individual's past experiences that can shape an individual's outlook, leading to a defensive and skeptical mind set, environmental influences: being surrounded by negativity, whether from family, friends, or co-workers, low self-esteem: individuals with low self-esteem may adopt a negative attitude as a protective mechanism, avoiding disappointment by expecting the worst., stress and fatigue can diminish one's ability to maintain a positive outlook, lack of purpose, without a clear sense of direction or goals, individuals may struggle to find motivation and positivity which can result to personal relationship, professional impact, mental health, physical health and opportunity lost. Some of the attitude of Business Educators toward adopting artificial intelligence applications in teaching Business Education courses maybe as a result of their acceptability level, concern about potential job displacement, ethical concerns, possible resource limitations, level of resistance (Amaewhule, Okiridu & Nwoko, 2019).

The acceptability level of business educators toward adopting artificial intelligence (AI) applications in teaching Business Education courses generally refers to the extent to which educators are open to, willing to, and comfortable with integrating artificial intelligence technologies into their instructional practices. This concept is often measured by assessing attitudes, perceptions, and readiness among educators regarding artificial intelligence tools in educational settings, also Business educators may have several ethical concerns regarding the adoption of artificial intelligence (AI) applications in teaching Business Education courses. These concerns stem from the potential risks artificial intelligence poses to privacy, fairness, academic integrity, and the human-centric nature of education (Blessing, 2022). Another area is the concern about potential job displacement among Business Educators regarding the adoption of artificial intelligence (AI) in teaching Business Education courses arises from the fear that artificial intelligence technologies could reduce the need for human educators by automating certain teaching tasks. This apprehension reflects broader workforce anxieties about automation and technological advancements across various sectors, including education. Business educators may face several resource limitations when adopting artificial intelligence (AI) in teaching Business Education courses. These constraints can hinder the effective integration of artificial intelligence tools and technologies in educational settings. Artificial Intelligence is transforming education and modern business and those changes will only accelerate over time. The business world needs agile and collaborative problem-solvers to manage these global changes, and today, Artificial intelligence advancements increasingly happen in higher education settings, driven by educators, learners, faculty members, and institutions. Besides, institutions are realizing opportunities to incorporate Artificial Intelligence to create more adaptive learning environments and augment education with analytics, creative tools, and automated labour. Al-Jabri and Al-Issawi (2020) sees artificial intelligence as a nomenclature assigned to a spectrum of novel methods and programming techniques utilized to develop accounting systems that emulate certain facets of human intelligence.

In the same vein, Ryan (2021) remarked that the integration of educational technology in education systems and teaching brings forth a multitude of benefits that extend beyond the conventional classroom setting, and the emergence of AI-driven personalized learning, the accessibility of online courses, and the interactive engagement of educational technology tools have revolutionized the field of education. In furtherance, Artificial intelligence has created a new environment for teaching and learning, thus leading to further collaborations among students and many universities like University of Ibadan, University Of Lagos, Covenant University, Ahmadu Bello University have started using Artificial intelligence application services and systems for teaching and learning such as Teacher Bot application, Fetchy, application Google AI application, Quillbot application and IBM's Watson application (Teaching Assistant) which afford an automated teacher presence throughout the course duration (Popenici & Kerr, 2017). Consequently, students develop skills that are needed for employment opportunities, self-sustainability and economic survival. Supporting the above assertions, Pence (2019) has it that Artificial

Intelligence would bring about massive employment improvement by eliminating 1.8 million jobs and then creating 2.3 million new jobs. Thus, Business Educators and students are required to be prepared for such transitions, Universities and colleges would be vital in the future because they would become a major power and source for most of the Artificial intelligence innovation centres worldwide (MOE, 2018). More so, the infusion of Artificial Intelligence into the educational space holds a plethora of potential for improving learning outcomes by offering carefully tailored tutoring solutions, streamlining continuous assessment processes, and fostering interactive learning experiences between virtual assistants and Business Education students. Moreover, Wogboroma (2022) opined that higher education benefits from Artificial Intelligence through four major areas such as student success, teaching and learning, academic research and, secure and connect campus. Thus, HEIs are expected to produce a high-quality and skilful workforce. Besides, Business Educators would have to be faced with new experiences and opportunities which they need to brace up to. Consequently, this situation would enable Business Education curriculum planners to identify and properly include Artificial Intelligence in the syllabus and the style of teaching, thereby bringing Business Education programmes into new instructional styles.

In today's rapidly evolving technological landscape, artificial intelligence has emerged as a key player in various industries and education. Its potential in teaching has been significant, with the ability to complement traditional teaching methods, provide customized learning experiences, and equip students with the necessary skills to succeed in the ever-changing business world. Tuomi (2018) viewed Artificial Intelligence as the sophisticated capabilities of computers that enable them to mimic human cognitive functions and it encompasses a broad range of activities, from language comprehension and problem-solving to medical diagnostics and autonomous vehicle navigation. Typically, Artificial intelligence is characterized by its capacity to execute duties that would normally require human intelligence, thereby extending the boundaries of machine-enabled functionalities. Artificial Intelligence's versatility and advanced computational skills are transforming various sectors, enhancing efficiency, and contributing to advancements in technology and society. Supporting the above views, Ashok (2020) described Artificial Intelligence as a suite of software technologies that possess one or more of the following functionalities; the ability to recognize and interpret audio, visual, textual, and tactile inputs, such as facial recognition, the capacity to make informed decisions. Also, it has the capability to autonomously extract knowledge and identify patterns within data, which is useful in discerning misinformation on social platforms; the facility for interactive communication, utilized in chatbots and social robotics; and the aptitude for logical reasoning.

Artificial Intelligence according to Suo (2022), is the development of computer systems that can perform tasks that normally require human intelligence, such as problem-solving, language processing, and decision-making. Also, Bupo and Akpomi (2023) contended that Artificial Intelligence is the replication of human intelligence patterns by computer systems, codes or machines to act and reason like humans. It is the science of engineering of making intelligent machines, especially intelligent computer programs and It is related to the similar task of using computers to understand human intelligence, but Artificial Intelligence does not have to confine itself to methods that are biologically observable (McCarthy, 2014). Similarly, One of the main applications of Artificial Intelligence in teaching Business Education courses is the development of intelligent tutoring systems. Intelligent tutoring systems can evaluate written assignments, multiple-choice tests, and even simulations. This reduces the time and effort required by Business Educators, allowing them to focus on providing qualitative feedback and addressing higher-order thinking skills. Additionally, AI-powered analytics can provide Business Educators with valuable insights into student performance patterns, identifying areas of difficulty and enabling them to make data-driven instructional decisions. Furthermore, it allows Business Educators to better focus their teaching efforts on those specific areas requiring attention or offer additional tests for strengthening Business education students. Also, incorporating Artificial Intelligence into educational platforms offers interactive learning experiences and promotes a dynamic learning atmosphere where students feel supported all through their academic journey. Artificial Intelligence's role in Business Education is multifaceted, with implications for curriculum development, teaching methodologies, and student engagement (Amaewhule & Agburuga, 2019).

According to Suo (2022) the use of artificial intelligence in teaching Business Education courses has gained significant attention in recent years. In the context of Business Education, Artificial intelligence has the potential to enhance the learning experience, personalize instruction, and provide valuable insights for both students and educators. Furthermore, Suo (2022) buttressed that artificial intelligence systems use machine learning algorithms to analyze student performance, identify areas of improvement, deliver personalized instruction, and can provide tailored feedback, track progress, and guide students through complex business concepts and its personalized learning approach ensures that Business Education students receive a more comprehensive understanding of the subject matter, leading to improved academic performance. According to Mescon (2020), Business Educators must prepare students for collaboration and success with Artificial intelligence, even as they help students adapt to the idea of sharing responsibilities with artificial intelligence. In the same vein, Igbokwe (2023) posited that the application of Artificial Intelligence in Business Education extends beyond the classroom and it provides several benefits, such as personalized learning experiences, efficient assessment methods, and the capacity to simulate real-world business scenarios. Also, Igbokwe further stated that Artificial Intelligence applications can assist in marketing, recruiting, and admissions, streamlining processes and providing insights that were previously unattainable. In the realm of lifelong learning and executive education, Artificial intelligence opens up new avenues for continuous professional development, allowing business educators to stay abreast of the latest trends and technologies.

The incorporation of artificial intelligence in Business Education is influenced by various factors, such as perceived advantages, institutional support, and personal attitudes towards technology (Bancoro, 2024). Recent research has suggested that Business Educators who possess a deeper understanding of Artificial Intelligence and its applications are more inclined to integrate it into their courses. Additionally, institutions that provide sufficient training and resources for Artificial Intelligence integration can foster a more favourable environment for its adoption. Hence, it is imperative to acknowledge the significance of Artificial Intelligence in Business Education and advocate for its adoption. Olatunde-Aiyedun (2024) postulated that tertiary institutions must provide adequate support to Business Educators and students to facilitate the smooth integration of Artificial Intelligence into the curriculum. By doing so, Business Educators can create a comprehensive and dynamic learning environment that prepares students for the demands of the future workforce.

Statement of the Problem

Artificial Intelligence (AI) in education bridges the gap between teaching and learning by enhancing the learning experience, personalizing instruction, and providing valuable insights for both students and educators. The use of artificial intelligence applications in teaching Business Education courses has gained significant attention in recent years due to its potential to transform education by making learning more effective and adaptive to individual student needs. Artificial Intelligence can support educators by automating repetitive tasks, enabling data-driven decision-making, and fostering a collaborative web-based learning culture. Moreover, the continuous acceleration of technological innovations, including artificial intelligence, has created an urgent need for Business Educators to acquire the knowledge, skills, and experiences necessary for the 21st-century classroom. Today's classrooms require educators with the requisite competencies in artificial intelligence to remain relevant in their profession while preparing students to adapt to the evolving demands of a technology-driven workplace (Akpomi & Bupo, 2023).

Despite the numerous benefits, there are significant barriers hindering the adoption and utilization of artificial intelligence applications in teaching Business Education courses. Observations indicate that the attitude of Business Educators plays a crucial role in determining the extent to which artificial intelligence tools are embraced, especially in a world where commerce and businesses are increasingly ICT-driven. Several attitudes have been identified as obstacles to artificial intelligence adoption in the teaching of Business Education courses, which includes acceptability level, varying degrees of openness and readiness to embrace artificial intelligence technologies, concern about potential job displacement, fear that AI could replace teaching roles or diminish the educator's significance, ethical concerns, issues related to data privacy, bias, and intellectual property. level of resistance, reluctance, fear of change, and risk aversion, possible resource limitations, lack of access to adequate technological infrastructure,

professional development, and institutional support, and inadequate power supply in tertiary institution, since artificial intelligence cannot function effectively without steady power supply. Thus, it is based on the above gaps that this study is designed to examine the attitude of Business Educators toward adopting artificial intelligence applications in teaching Business Education courses in Universities in Rivers State.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study was to examine the attitude of Business Educators toward adopting Artificial Intelligence applications in teaching Business Education courses in Universities in Rivers State. Specifically, the study sought to.

1. Examine the acceptability level of Business Educators in adopting artificial intelligence applications in teaching Business Education courses in Rivers State Universities.
2. Examine the concern about job displacement among Business Educators in adopting artificial intelligence in teaching Business Education courses in Universities in Rivers State.

Research Questions

The following research questions were used for the study.

1. What is the acceptability level of Business Educators in adopting artificial intelligence applications in teaching Business Education courses in Universities in Rivers State?
2. What is the concern about potential job displacement among Business Educators in adopting artificial intelligence in teaching Business Education courses in Universities in Rivers State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses formulated were tested at 0.05 level significance.

1. There is no significant difference in the mean responses of lecturers in Rivers State University, University of Port-Harcourt and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education on the acceptability level of Business Educators in adopting artificial intelligence applications in teaching Business Education courses.
2. There is no significant difference in the mean responses of lecturers in Rivers State University, University of Port-Harcourt and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education on the concern about job displacement among Business Educators in adopting artificial intelligence in teaching Business Education courses.

METHODOLOGY

This study adopted the descriptive survey design. Descriptive research is the research design in which data is collected in a qualitative manner and analyzed using quantitative procedures'

The area of this study was Rivers State Universities. The population of the study consisted of 47 Business Educators. This comprises of all Business Educators in Rivers State University (RSU) Port Harcourt and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education. Due to the fact that the population of the study is relatively small, census sampling method. This means that the entire respondents of forty-seven (47) Business Educators were used for analyses of the study. The instrument for data collection is a researcher structured questionnaire, titled "Attitude of Business Educators in Adopting Artificial Intelligence Applications in Teaching Business Education Courses. The instrument was subjected to face and content validity. In order to establish the reliability of the instrument, test-retest method was adopted. The reliability of the instrument was determined using Pearson product moment correlation coefficient (PPMCC) and the result was 0.89 which revealed that the research instrument is reliable to measure what it is meant to measure. The researcher engaged the services of two (2) assistants who helped to administer the instrument to the respondents. Data collected was analysed using mean and standard deviation to answer the five (5) research questions, while ANNOVA with the aid of SPSS was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The decision rule for the research questions was any point equal and above 3.00 was considered high extent, while any point below 3.00 was considered low extent.

PRESENTATION OF RESULTS

Research Question 1: *What is the acceptability level of Business Educators in adopting artificial intelligence applications in teaching Business Education courses in Universities in Rivers State?*

Table 4.1: Computed Means and Standard Deviations Scores of Respondents on acceptability level of Business Educators in adopting artificial intelligence applications in teaching Business Education courses in Universities in Rivers State. (N=36)

S/N	Items	\bar{x}	S.D	Remark
1.	Actively using AI tools for teaching, assessments, and student engagement	4.00	.756	HE
2.	Open to exploring AI applications in teaching but with some reservations.	3.89	.398	HE
3	May still rely on traditional methods alongside AI tools	4.06	.674	VHE
4	Willing to use AI tools but lacks strong motivation or understanding.	3.97	.736	HE
5	May require more training and support to increase acceptance.	3.28	.615	HE
6	Completely opposed to AI adoption in teaching practices.	3.94	.630	HE
Grand Mean/S.D		3.86	.635	HE

Source: **Researcher’s Field Survey** (2025) (Details in appendix D).

The result in table 4.1 shows the acceptability level of Business Educators in adopting artificial intelligence applications in teaching Business Education courses in Universities in Rivers State with the grand mean and standard deviation scores of 3.86 and 0.64 respectively. The five out of six items indicate to a high extent Business Educators in adopting artificial intelligence applications, while item three is to a very high extent.

Research Question 2: *What is the concern about potential job displacement among Business Educators in adopting artificial intelligence in teaching Business Education courses in Universities in Rivers State?*

Table 4.2: Computed Means and Standard Deviations Scores of Respondents on concern about potential job displacement among Business Educators in adopting artificial intelligence in teaching Business Education courses in Universities in Rivers State. (N=36)

S/N	Items	\bar{x}	S.D	Remark
1.	Fear that AI tools may automate core teaching tasks, reducing the need for human educators.	3.56	.809	HE
2.	Concern that AI platforms could deliver lectures, grade assignments, and provide feedback without human involvement.	3.89	.747	HE
3	Concern that AI cannot fully replace mentorship, emotional intelligence, and personalized feedback.	3.97	.167	HE
4	Perception that AI could diminish the role of educators as knowledge authorities	3.72	.615	HE
5	Concern that older educators may struggle to adapt to new technologies.	3.83	.447	HE
Grand Mean/ S.D		3.794	.557	HE

Researcher’s Field Survey (2025) (Details in appendix D).

Data contained in table 4.2 shows that there is a growing fear that AI tools may automate core teaching tasks, reducing the need for human educators. The result in items 1 to 5 showed that there is concern

about potential job displacement among Business Educators in adopting artificial intelligence in teaching Business Education courses in Universities in Rivers State with the mean and standard deviation scores of 3.80 and 0.56 meaning to a high extent

Testing of Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference in the mean responses of lecturers in Rivers State University, University of Port-Harcourt and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education on the acceptability level of Business Educators in adopting artificial intelligence applications in teaching Business Education courses.

Table 4.6: ANOVA on the Mean Ratings of lecturers in Rivers State University, University of Port-Harcourt and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education on the acceptability level of Business Educators in adopting artificial intelligence applications in teaching Business Education courses.

Sources of Variance	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	.275	2	.138	2.260	.120
Within Groups	2.011	33	.061		
Total	2.286	35			

Source: Researcher’s Field Survey (2025) (Details in appendix D)

From table 4.6, the F value of 2.260 is greater than the Sign value of .120 at 0.05% level of significance and degree of freedom of 2 and 36. While the sum of squares (SS) for between groups was .275 and the (mean sum of squares (MS) .138, for within groups (Error Variance), it was 2.011 and .061 respectively. Thus, the null hypothesis of no significant difference in the mean ratings of lecturers in Rivers State University, University of Port-Harcourt and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education on the acceptability level of Business Educators in adopting artificial intelligence applications in teaching Business Education courses was rejected meaning there is significant difference in the mean ratings of lecturers in Rivers State University, University of Port-Harcourt and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education on the acceptability level of Business Educators in adopting artificial intelligence applications in teaching Business Education courses.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference in the mean responses of lecturers in Rivers State University, University of Port-Harcourt and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education on the concern about job displacement among Business Educators in adopting artificial intelligence in teaching Business Education courses.

Table 4.7: ANOVA on the Mean Ratings of lecturers in Rivers State University, University of Port-Harcourt and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education on the concern about job displacement among Business Educators in adopting artificial intelligence in teaching Business Education courses.

Sources of Variance	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	.420	2	.210	2.100	.139
Within Groups	3.299	33	.100		
Total	3.719	35			

Source: Researcher’s Field Survey (2025) (Details in appendix D)

From table 4.7, the F value of 2.100 is greater than the sign value of .139 at 0.05% level of significance and degree of freedom of 2 and 36. While the sum of squares (SS) for between groups was .420 and the (mean sum of squares (MS) .210, for within groups (Error Variance), it was 3.299 and .100 respectively. Thus, the null hypothesis of no significant difference in the mean ratings of lecturers in Rivers State University, University of Port-Harcourt and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education on the concern about job displacement among Business Educators in adopting artificial intelligence in teaching Business Education courses was rejected meaning there is significant difference in the mean ratings of lecturers in Rivers State University, University of Port-Harcourt and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education on the concern about job displacement among Business Educators in adopting artificial intelligence in teaching Business Education courses.

Summary of Major Findings

Major findings from the research work are as follows:

1. That acceptability level of Business Educators in adopting artificial intelligence applications in teaching Business Education courses in Universities in Rivers State to a High Extent.
2. That concern about potential job displacement among Business Educators in adopting artificial intelligence in teaching Business Education courses in Universities in Rivers State to a High Extent.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Research Question and hypothesis 1: The findings revealed that Business Educators in Universities agreed that actively using AI tools for teaching, assessments, and student engagement, may require more training and support to increase acceptance. The findings are in line with Farah in Olatunde-Aiyedun (2024) this willingness is influenced by factors like perceived usefulness, ease of use, institutional support, and concerns about job security and ethical implications, also Adekunle, Temitayo, Adelana, Aruleba, and Sunday in Igbokwe (2023), teachers' confidence in their ability to teach artificial intelligence significantly predicts their intention to integrate artificial intelligence into their teaching practice, underscoring their perception of its usefulness and educational relevance. The test of hypothesis one indicates that South-South Public Universities students do differ significantly in their mean rating regarding lecturers in Rivers State University, University of Port-Harcourt and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education on the acceptability level of Business Educators in adopting artificial intelligence applications in teaching Business Education courses.

Research Question and hypothesis 2: The findings of the study in research question two showed that Business Educators fear that AI tools may automate core teaching tasks, reducing the need for human educators, concern that AI platforms could deliver lectures, grade assignments, and provide feedback without human involvement, Perception that AI could diminish the role of educators as knowledge authorities. This result is in line with the views of Al-Zyoud, (2020) the concern about potential job displacement refers to the fear or apprehension that artificial intelligence technologies might reduce the need for human instructors by automating tasks traditionally performed by educators, potentially leading to job losses or diminished roles in the teaching profession (Al-Zyoud, 2020). However, Bughin, Seong, Manyika, Chui, & Joshi in Suo (2021) The McKinsey Global Institute estimates that by 2030, at least 70% of companies will adopt some form of artificial intelligence technology, and 60% of current occupations could face automation within the next decade. As artificial intelligence grows more sophisticated, job displacement is inevitable. Also the test of hypothesis one indicates that Business Educators do differ significantly in their mean rating regarding lecturers in Rivers State University, University of Port-Harcourt and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education on the concern about job displacement among Business Educators in adopting artificial intelligence in teaching Business Education courses.

CONCLUSION

The study examined the attitude of Business Educators toward adopting Artificial Intelligence (AI) applications in teaching Business Education courses. The findings revealed that while there is a growing

awareness of AI technologies among Business Educators, their attitudes toward full adoption remain mixed, shaped by factors such as digital competence, perceived usefulness, institutional support, and fear of job displacement. Educators who possess higher levels of technological literacy and who receive adequate institutional training and resources tend to exhibit more positive attitudes toward integrating AI tools into their teaching practices.

Despite the evident benefits of AI such as personalized learning, automated grading, and improved instructional efficiency, barriers such as lack of infrastructure, resistance to change, and limited professional development opportunities hinder its widespread adoption in Business Education. This underscores the need for targeted training programs, infrastructure upgrades, and policy support to build educators' confidence and skills in utilizing AI effectively.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study the following recommendations were made:

1. Educational policymakers and university management should build on the already high acceptability level by organizing regular hands-on workshops and certification programs on AI tools for teaching, to reinforce and expand Business Educators' willingness to adopt these technologies across universities.
2. University administrators should engage Business Educators in transparent dialogue and professional development initiatives that emphasize AI as a supportive teaching aid rather than a replacement, to reduce fear of job displacement and promote collaborative human-AI teaching models.

REFERENCES

- Akpomi, M. E., & Bupo, G. O. (2019). Perception of business education students towards online assessment via a learning management system. *Rivers State University Journal of Education*, 22(1&2), 1-9.
- Al-Jabri, Z.M.O., & Al-Issawi, I. (2020). Artificial diversity and its role in Emirati Human Genome Project (study in the light of Islamic Jurisprudence) (p.209).
- Amaewhule, W.A. & Agburuga, V. (2019). Influence of mentoring on entrepreneurship development of business education students in public tertiary institutions in Rivers State. *International Journal of Business & Law Research* 7(4):50-58.
- Amaewhule, W.A., Okiridu, O.S.F. & Nwoko, N.L. (2019). E-mentoring preparation of beginning business education teachers in Nigeria Universities. *Nigerian Journal of Business Education (NIGJBED)*. 6(2),73-83
- Bancoro, J.C. M. (2024). The relationship between artificial intelligence (AI) usage and Academic performance of business Administration students. *International Journal of Asian Business and Management* 3(1).
- Bupo, G. O., & Akpomi, M. E. (2023). Artificial intelligence, robotics, and information communication technologies: Tools for enhancing business and educational management. *Journal of Business and Entrepreneurship Education*, 2(1), 21-29.
- Igbokwe, I.C., (2023). Application of artificial intelligence (AI) in educational management 13(3), ISSN 2250-3153
- Mescon, T. (2020). The impact of artificial intelligence in business education. *AACSB*.
- Olatunde-Aiyedun T.G. (2024). Artificial intelligence (AI) in Education: Integration of AI into science education curriculum in Nigerian universities. *International Journal of Artificial Intelligence for Digital*, 1(1).
- Popenici, S. A. D., & Kerr, S. (2017). Exploring the importance of artificial intelligence on teaching and learning in higher education. *Research and Practice in Technology Enhanced Learning*, 12(1), 1-15.

- Ryan, T. Y. (2021). Artificial intelligence in education: Bringing it all together. In *OECD Digital Education Outlook 2021: Pushing the frontiers with AI, blockchain, and robotics* (pp. 43-56). OECD Library.
- Suo, H. (2021). Design and development of educational robot teaching resources using artificial intelligence technology. *International Journal of Educational Technology (iJET)*, 16(5), 116-129.
- Tuomi, I. (2018). The impact of artificial intelligence on learning, teaching, and education: Policies for the future. In M. Cabrera, R. Vuorikari, & Y. Punie (Eds.), *EUR 29442 EN* (pp. 1-22). Publications Office of the European Union. <https://doi.org/10.2760/12297>
- Wogboroma, N. (2022). Entrepreneurial self-motivation skill acquisition for self-sustainability by postgraduate business education students in Rivers State. *African Journal of Business and Economic Development*, 2(1), 41-47.